

“Formulation of Polyherbal Immuno-boosting Avaleha”

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ABSTRACT

Avaleha kalpana is one among the mostly used dosage form in Ayurveda. Its appreciable qualities are shelf-life, agreeable taste, easy administration, highly nutritional, and better potency etc. Avaleha is a kalpana semi solid formulation of drugs, prepared with addition of honey, sugar or sugar candy and boiled with required drug juice or decoction it is known as Avaleha. While preparation of Avaleha Madhura Dravya's like Guda or Sharkara and honey are added to the juice or the decoction.

(**Keywords:** Herbal Avaleha; immunity booster; Honey base immunity booster; herbs; Avaleha kalpana)

INTRODUCTION

We summarised different herbs Shatawari (Asparagus), Ashwagandha (Withania somnifera), Giloy (Tinospora cordifolia), Ginger (Ginger officinalis Turmeric (Curcuma longa) Cardomom (Elettaria cardamomum) Aloe vera (aloebarbadensis) Amla (phyllanthus emblica) Honey (Apis mellifera), Almond (prunus dulcis), sugar candy.

Avaleha

Avaleha or Leha is a semi solid dosage form of Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals intended for internal administration. It is prepared by addition of sugar candy and boiled with prescribed drug powdered mixture. It can also be consumed along with some adjuvant. The Avaleha word has been derived from the root word "lihaswadane", in which lih' means substance which can be licked and 'aswadane' which means that has good taste. According to Acharya Sharangdhara, the semisolid mass of avaleha obtained by continuously heating of Kwathadi basic Kalpanas is called Rasakriya.

Synonyms:

- Lehya
- Leha
- Avaleha
- Rasakriya
- Ghana etc.

Basic contents of Avaleha:

- Liquid medium (Drava Dravya)
- Substrate (Madhura Dravya)
- Medicinal part (Aushadha Dravya or Kalka Dravya)
- Adjuvants (Prakshepa Dravya)

IMPORTANCE OF AVALEHA:

- It has more shelf life period (or more stability)
- More palatable, because it contains sweetening agents and that's way it can be easily taken by child and adult.
- Avaleha Kalpana contains Madhura Dravya and Sneha Dravyas, these both work as preventatives and increase the shelf period.
- **MATERIAL AND METHODS**
- Shatawari, Ashwagandha, Giloy, Alovera, Amla, Almond, Tulsi, Turmeric, Ginger, Cardamom, Honey, Sugarcandy were purchased from local market.
- FORMULA:

Sr.No.	Ingredients	Quantity Taken	Uses
1	Shatawari	50gm	Enhance reproductive health.
2	Ashwagandha	50gm	Manage stress&anxiety
3	Giloy	2gm	Boost immunity
4	Alovera	2gm	Healing property
5	Almond	10gm	Lower blood sugar
6	Amla	30gm	Liver detoxification

7	Turmeric	2gm	Wound healing
8	Ginger	10gm	Anti-inflammatory
9	Cardamom	0.50gm	Digestive aid
10	Honey	250ml	Anti-oxidant
11	Sugar candy	250gm	Sugar free option
12	Tulsi	0.64gm	Respiratory health
13	Ghee	100ml	Boost immunity system
14	water	Qs.	

PROCEDURE

- All the required parts of plant are powdered and passed through sieve no 180 separately to obtain fine powder.
- As per textual description 10 drugs described above were powdered separately and mixed as per quantity mentioned above.
- Then 100ml ghee is added to the wide mouthed vessel and heat it in a low flame.
- Then we add almond powder in melted ghee and roast it.
- After that amla powder is added and mixed it properly.
- Then we add honey to the powdered mixture.
- After that whole powdered mixture of plants added and mix it by continuously stirring by adding sufficient amount of water in it.
- Last but not least we add sugarcandy to maintain sweetness of preparation.

Storage:

It should be stored in air tight container like glass jar, now a days it is stored in plastic container because it is non- reactive and easy to use, whereas metal container can be reactive to avaleha but it depends on contents which used in avaleha.

Savirvata Avadhi (Shelf life) :

6 Month to 1 year when stored properly in a dry and cool place, away from moisture and direct sunlight.

Anupana (Adjuvants) :

Anupamas are the drava dravyas which can be taken after consuming avaleha. Its commonly a liquid which helps the avalea to digest properly & increase effectiveness of avaleha. It helps in proper absorption. Commonly used anupanas are ghee, milk, juices, honey, warm water.

Sevana kala (time of administration):

Best time of administration is in early morning, on an empty stomach, before the sun rise. Early morning the digestive fire [agni] is strongest, which is belived to enhance better absorption of the herbs nutrients and vitamins.

The metabolic processes of body are more active in the morning.

Result and Discussion**RESULT:**

Parameter	Observation
Appearance	Viscos and sticky
Color	Dark brown
Odor	Distinctive odor
Texture	Semi-solid and slightly thick
Taste	Sweet

DISCUSSION:

Immuno-boosting avaleha have various positive effects on the body, by enhancing immune function and overall well-being.

CONCLUSION

- ❖ Avaleha kalpana is most important kalpana since ancient time. Now a day's it is gaining popularity because of its easy route of administration.
- ❖ The prepared formulation is beneficial for all the persons because the formulation is prepared from natural herbs so the chances of side or adverse effects are lower.
- ❖ This is good supplement for freshly recover from the illness and gives the freshness to the person.
- ❖ All the herbs used in this formulation are easily available in any season and less expensive.

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